

Sulphonamidobromophthaleins

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Organic bromo compounds, such as, eosine¹, sulphobromophthalein², mercurochrome³, etc., are widely used in medicine. 3',3''-Disulphanilylamidophenolphthalein was synthesised by van Kampen and others⁴. Recently sulphonamidoiodophthaleins have been prepared by Mehta and co-workers⁵. The present work has been undertaken with a view to preparing 5',5''-dibromo-3',3''-disulphanilylamidophenolphthalein and its derivatives for the study of their physiological properties.

5',5''-Dibromo-3',3''-dinitrophenolphthalein (II).—3',3''-Dinitrophenolphthalein⁶ (I: m.p. 198-99°) (3 g.) in glacial acetic acid (125 ml) was treated with bromine (9 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) and the mixture kept at 55° for 2 hours with occasional shaking. After 24 hours, on adding cold water it afforded a bright yellow precipitate which was collected, dissolved in NaOH, treated with sodium sulphite, and reprecipitated with HCl. The product on washing with water and acetic acid furnished the dinitrophenolphthalein (II), m.p. 238-40°, yield 85-87%. (Found: C, 42.28; H, 1.81; N, 4.75; Br, 28.42. $C_{20}H_{10}O_8N_2Br_2$ requires C, 42.43; H, 1.78; N, 4.95; Br, 28.23%).

The product (II) is a bright yellow powder, soluble in acetone and chloroform, sparingly soluble in ethanol, and insoluble in ether, petroleum, etc. It slowly dissolves in H_2SO_4 (conc.), forming an orange-red solution which on dilution with water throws down the substance with disappearance of the colour. It dissolves in alkali and alkali carbonates with an orange-yellow colour and can be completely precipitated on adding HCl.

5',5''-Dibromo-3',3''-diaminophenolphthalein (III).—A fresh 20% solution of sodium hydrosulphite in water (25 ml) was quickly added with vigorous shaking to a solution of the preceding compound (II) (2 g.) in hot acetone (100 ml). The reaction was spontaneous, colour of the solution changing from bright yellow to straw-yellow. The completion of the reaction was marked by a blue colour on adding a solution of NaOH to a few drops of the reaction mixture.

The acetone was removed by distillation to obtain a brown solid which was treated with 5% HCl and subsequent addition of a 2% aqueous solution of NaOH at pH 6.5-6.8 provided a colorless solid. The solid was dissolved in minimum quantity of ethanol, water was added to turbidity, and it was set aside. Repeated treatment in this manner finally

1. Bayer, *Annalen*, 1876, 183, 38; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1922, III, 1187.

2. The Merck Index, VII Ed., Merck & Co., Inc., Rahway, N. J., U.S.A., 1960, p. 166.

3. Ouel-Farrer, "United States Dispensatory," XXV Ed., J. B. Lippincott Co., Philadelphia, 1960, p. 806.

4. Graessland and van Kampen, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1961, 46, 3492.

5. Mehta et al., *Curr. Sci.*, 1961, 30, 480.

6. Van Kampen, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1952, 71, 954.

furnished 5',5''-dibromo-3',3'''-diaminophenolphthalein (III); it did not melt up to 360° but sintered at 120-22°; yield 40-41%. (Found: C, 47.42; H, 2.46; N, 5.62; Br, 31.75. $C_{20}H_{14}O_4N_2Br_2$ requires C, 47.45; H, 2.78; N, 5.53; Br, 31.58%).

It is a colorless, amorphous powder, soluble in ethanol and acetone, and insoluble in ether and light petroleum. It forms with H_2SO_4 (conc.) a red solution which on dilution with water becomes light yellow without forming any precipitate. It dissolves in alkali and alkali carbonates with a deep blue colour. When diazotised, it shows an orange-red colour with β -naphthol.

Acid or alkaline reduction of (II) with metals, like iron or tin, did not succeed as the bromine was eliminated from the compound.

5',5''-Dibromo-3', 3'''-diacetylsulphanilylamidophenolphthalein (IV).—*N*-Acetylsulphanilyl chloride⁷ (m.p. 149°) (4.6 g.) was added with occasional shaking to a solution of the preceding compound (III) (5 g.) in acetone (75 ml), ethanol (45 ml), and pyridine (7.5 ml). The mixture was kept in a stoppered flask and left overnight at the room temperature; the colour of the solution in the meantime changed from deep yellow to red. On concentration and removal of pyridine, a viscous liquid resulted which on dilution with water afforded a bulky light brown solid. All attempts to crystallise this brown product from organic solvents did not succeed. Repeated treatment of dissolving this solid in ethanol and precipitating with water furnished 5',5''-dibromo-3', 3'''-diacetylsulphanilylamidophenolphthalein (IV), m.p. 220-22°, yield 50-55%. (Found: C, 48.20; H, 3.05; N, 6.36; Br, 17.55; S, 7.30. $C_{36}H_{28}O_{10}N_2Br_2S_2$ requires C, 48.01; H, 3.13; N, 6.22; Br, 17.75; S, 7.12%).

It is a colorless amorphous powder, soluble in ethanol and acetone, and insoluble in ether and light petroleum. It is insoluble in HCl but dissolves in alkali and alkali carbonates with a blue colour.

5',5''-Dibromo-3',3'''-disulphanilylamidophenolphthalein (V).—The dibromodiacetyl compound (IV) (1g.) was hydrolysed with a 4% aqueous solution of NaOH (20 ml) at 100°. The solution was cooled, diluted with water, and adjusted to pH 6.5-6.8 with 5% HCl when a bulky precipitate of compound (V) was obtained. It could not be crystallised from commoner organic solvents. Its purification by dissolving the precipitate in ethanol and reprecipitating it with water finally yielded a white solid, m.p. 202-204° (decomp.), yield 85-90%. (Found: C, 47.26; H, 2.98, N, 6.68; Br, 19.83; S, 8.01. $C_{32}H_{24}O_8N_4Br_2S_2$ requires C, 47.03; H, 2.96; N, 6.86; Br, 19.57; S, 7.85%).

It is a colorless amorphous powder, soluble in ethanol and acetone but insoluble in ether. It dissolves in dilute alkali with a blue colour and in acid with a yellow colour. The ethanolic solution of the substance developed a light green colour with ethanolic ferric chloride and an orange-red colour on diazotisation and treatment with β -naphthol solution.

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